

Implementation Of An Integrated Router Security Framework For Protecting Computer Networks

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ABSTRACT

Reliable and secure routing is essential for the connectivity of critical communications networks, ensuring that data packets reach their intended destinations without being intercepted, altered or dropped. Trust is a degree of belief about the future behaviours of other entities; trust alone is no longer enough. Trust must be paired with a new element - Recommendation. Trust + Recommendation = TrustR. TrustR serves as an independent, trusted third party within the framework. Routers are responsible for connecting different networks and forwarding data packets. It has great significance in computer networks, but also serves as a vehicle for various attacks. The objectives of this project are to implement the TrustR Framework, validate the data Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), Average end-to-end delay and analyse the performance of TrustR based on new parameter settings. The Ad hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV) routing protocol was employed. Used and modified an existing wireless network simulator in MATLAB for the simulation tests. Four data traffic flows are set, and the simulation time is 100s. Four kinds of attacks are deployed: unauthorised access, routing spoofing, BlackHole, and JellyFish. The experimental result demonstrates TrustR's ability to defend against attacks and improve network performance by improving the Data Packet Delivery Ratio and minimising BlackHole attacks, and also minimising the Average end-to-end delay and defending against unauthorised nodes.

Keywords: AODV, BlackHole, Node, Router, TrustR,

INTRODUCTION

A Computer Network enables data transfer among nodes, more especially heterogeneous nodes, e.g. your home or office network. It has an intermediate system that forwards/switches data from one link to another, e.g. routers and switches. Routers in a computer network serve as gateways that enable packets of bits to be forwarded separately. A router is a device that operates at layer 3 of the OSI model. The main function is path selection and packet forwarding. Routers determine the path for a packet by examining its destination IP address and consulting the routing table, which contains information on network paths. They use a set of rules to identify the most efficient route for each packet. **Static routing:** Configured manually, suitable for small or stable networks. **Dynamic routing:** Automatically updated based on network activity, ideal for large or changing networks. Routers are core network equipment in any organisation, so the security of the router is our major concern. "Computer Network Security is one of the key things required to be known for anybody doing anything, it doesn't really matter, whether programming, database, etc., you need to know network security" (Raj, J. 2020).

Fig 1: Router connection

However, Routers are responsible for connecting different networks and forwarding data packets (Abdelaziz, et.al. 2013). The functionality of a router can be split into data plane, control plane and management plane (Greenberg, et.al. 2005). Despite the great significance of routers in computer networking, they have also served as a vehicle for various security attacks (Abdelaziz et.al. 2013). The router is rather vulnerable because of its critical role.

Firstly, attacks can be categorised into three types: **unauthorised access** to network resources, such as IP address spoofing; **data-plane attacks** to prevent data packets from being successfully delivered, such as BlackHole and JellyFish; and **unprotected forwarding Information Base (FIB)** to forward packets in the data plane, but it could produce an incorrect FIB. Besides, the router would not forward packets correctly (Aad et.al. 2008). 3) control-plane attacks to disturb or disrupt network operations, such as routing spoofing.

However, Wang et.al. (2011) proposed an attribute-based similarity mechanism, which is a model based on the degree of similarity among nodes. Meanwhile, among the nodes, a trust value of neighbour nodes is determined according to a set of attributes assigned, which includes velocity, moving direction, encryption type, and affiliated organisation. In this model scenario, the trusted routing scheme comprises four steps, viz: next hop determination, similarity degree calculation, packet transmission, and behaviour recognition.

Alomari (2013) proposed to utilise random numbers with a timestamp in the nodes to protect the confidentiality and privacy of the nodes. First, random numbers are protected with secret values, and utilizing the hash functions to avoid forgery and copying. More so, the time frame is utilised to provide a solution to avoid replay attacks, and also to protect varying values to solve synchronisation problems. Firstly, the significance of this scheme is to utilise the hash function, secret value and time stamp to increase the authentication among the nodes whenever communication starts in the ad-hoc network.

According to Wei Z. et.al. (2014), a unified trust management scheme was proposed that enhances the security in MANETs. In the proposed trust management scheme, the trust model has two components: direct and indirect observations. Thus, direct observation works on the observer node where the trust

value is derived using Bayesian inference, which is a type of uncertain reasoning when the full probability model can be obtained. However, an indirect observation is known as secondhand information obtained from neighbour nodes of the observer node, and the trust value here is derived using the Dempster-Shafer theory (DST), is also another type of uncertain reasoning when the proposition of interest can be derived by an indirect method. Earliest, by combining these two components in the trust model, we can obtain more accurate trust values of the observed nodes in MANETs. More especially, our throughput and packet delivery ratio (PDR) can be improved significantly, with slightly increased average end-to-end delay and overhead of messages.

Wahab et.al. (2015) compare the main results that contributed to solving problems related to trust and reputation in the context of Web services. First, a high-level classification scheme partitions Web services into three main architectures: single, composite, and communities. First, a low-level classification categorises the trust and reputation models based on the technique used to build the trust value within each architecture. The authors discussed the challenging problem of having active malicious Web services in the composite and community-based architectures. Thus, it aims to be used by future researchers as a roadmap to explore new trust and reputation models for Web services, taking into account the shortcomings of the existing models.

Venkanna et.al. (2015) proposed an algorithm, Trust and Energy-based Ad hoc On Demand Distance Vector (TE-AODV), which improved and modified the normal AODV algorithm through the dynamic incorporation of trust and energy values among the nodes in the topology in order to achieve cooperative routing. Meanwhile, the source node selects the cooperative path rather than the shortest path, thereby isolating the malicious and selfish nodes in the TE-AODV. However, the TE-AODV routing algorithm isolates the malicious and selfish nodes and considerably increases the routing performance, such as packet delivery ratio and average end-to-end latency.

Shuaishuai et.al. (2016) proposed the TrustR framework, which employs a cryptographic authentication method and a trust-based AODV routing mechanism, then modified it before integrating it into TrustR as SA-AODV and T-AODV, respectively. Meanwhile, the shortcoming of these methods is that they are only able to detect very limited kinds of attacks. Furthermore, the FIB is rarely protected in current works. This scheme, SA-AODV, is used to authenticate the nodes broadcasting Route Request (RREQ) Messages, and only RREQ messages from authenticated nodes are processed and forwarded. While in T-AODV, the indirect trust value and energy value are not used. Means the trust-based routing policy is that a node will not forward RREQ messages to the nodes whose trust value is less than 0.5.

Retaining or choosing the best path for data packets to go in such a network presented some difficulties. Routing protocols are urged to be set up at every station and router in a network to reduce packet dropping, data packet loss, traffic volume transmitted or received by stations, load in any network, and response time for the page to be viewed. The authors Aastha Mishra et al. (2017) proposed a comparative examination of these performance metrics, which was carried out after several classes of routing protocols were set up for various scenarios. OPNET IT GURU EDUCATIONAL VERSION 14.5 Modeler is utilised to achieve a performance comparison.

According to Khanna et al. (2020), they address the problem of mitigating black hole attacks and their variations. Their paper presents a battery, efficiency, and stability-based trust mechanism that detects and prevents packet drop attacks before isolating them through the process of disseminating information verified by fair nodes. To counter both single and cooperative forms of attack, the proposed work operates in two modes. In advance mode, a set of trusted trace packets and procedures identifies cooperative attacking nodes, thereby breaking the cooperation among malicious nodes, whereas in standard mode, the promiscuous facility and trust update lead to the identification of an attack.

However, for Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) to increase reliability (cooperation) among sensor nodes, trust evaluation models are an essential security enhancement tool. Tayyab Khan and Karan Singh (2020) developed an Accurate and Efficient Distributed Trust Model for WSNs, which is presented in their research, with an emphasis on security enhancement and basic criteria (resource efficiency). Compared to previous state-of-the-art trust models like LDTS, ADTC, LWTM, etc., the suggested mathematical model

(TSTM) computes communication and data (transmitted) trustworthiness more precisely and accurately. The proposed approach features special characteristics, including scheduler-based node trust, authentication-based data trust, and resistance to attacks through a high penalty and low incentive for node disobedience. Because trust values are consistent, the suggested trust model would be able to provide security against a variety of internal threats.

Mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) are widely used to realise various real-time applications due to the increase in ad hoc devices. However, ad hoc devices are vulnerable to a variety of security threats, including wormholes, black holes, and grey holes. Consequently, it is better to have an effective trust management protocol. This research proposes a unique gradient boost classifier. Additionally, h-non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm-III (hNSGA-III) is used to adjust the gradient boost classifier's hyperparameters. For experimental investigation, the optimised link state routing (OLSR) protocol is utilised. The blackhole, grayhole, and wormhole attacks on the OLSR are used to gather a multi-class dataset. The suggested hNSGA-III-based gradient boost classifier performs better than the competitive attack classification models, according to Jasleen Kaur and Supreet Kaur 2021, a comparative study.

For the purpose of identifying malicious nodes in the WSN, the authors suggested the Blackhole Attack Detection based on the Trust Calculation (BDTC) Mechanism. A tool for identifying black hole attacks has been added to identify malicious nodes. The communication type of attack in the network is developed by extending this method. This suggested method uses the innovative Weighted Clustering and Security Algorithm (WCSA) to select Cluster Heads while taking into account the battery life, mobility, ideal degree (number of neighbours), and transmission power of mobile nodes, Revathi, A.; Santhi, S. G. (2022).

Junjian, Y. et al. (2024) created a threat model-based approach and thoroughly examined 40 commercial off-the-shelf home routers, typical of recent models from 14 companies, to methodically assess potential threats. Eighty-one parameters and behaviours, including default and deep default settings, were surveyed. We identified several security vulnerabilities, including unencrypted firmware update communications, unsecured Wi-Fi networks, and simple admin passwords for "plug-and-play" routers, as well as insecure Wi-Fi security protocols and the exposure of IPv6 local devices due to a lack of firewall protection. Additionally, we found hidden WPS PIN support, which was occasionally connected to a trivial PIN. We are notifying the vendors about thirty exploitable vulnerabilities in total. In order to improve home network security, this study emphasises the necessity of closely examining default router settings and offers manufacturers and users useful insights. The authors' results highlight the significance of careful device configuration and encourage all parties involved to take proactive steps to reduce the risks associated with unsafe router default settings.

João Pereira et al. (2025) show that it is possible to validate a security-critical network component coherently, starting from high-level protocol models and ending with performance-optimised production code created by a separate team. In the process, we upgraded the security features of the protocol and found serious flaws and attacks in both the protocol and its implementation. This paper outlines the difficulties we encountered when verifying an existing real-world system, describes how we overcame these difficulties, summarises the key findings, and distils important lessons for safe system verification in the methods and resources used.

Furthermore, Jiasheng Zhou et al. (2025), the lack of a dynamic hop limit adjustment mechanism based on input and the rigidity of budget allocation across probing cycles are the two main issues with current approaches. A thorough understanding of IPv6 routing infrastructure is severely hampered by these issues, which result in the low hit rate and inefficiency of current router interface discovery techniques. In order to do this, we suggest Helixir, an effective, high hit-rate, feedback-based IPv6 router interface discovery system. The fundamental components of Helixir's architecture include a hop limit selection technique based on Thompson sampling, an inter-prefix budget allocation strategy that effectively balances exploration and exploitation, and a dynamic budget allocation mechanism spanning probing rounds. According to real-world testing, Helixir successfully finds over 31 million IPv6 router interface addresses in less than 30 minutes with a 100M budget, achieving a hit rate $3.64\times$ that of state-of-the-art algorithms on the BGP prefixes

dataset. Furthermore, a thorough security analysis of the identified router interfaces reveals that numerous devices expose hundreds of potential CVE vulnerabilities and open sensitive ports, underscoring the security threats in the IPv6 network.

Using APT threat models as a lens, this study offers a comprehensive security analysis of WLANs, classifying APT actors according to competence tiers and analysing their capacity to penetrate WLANs via logical attack surfaces. Radio Access Control interfaces, compromised insider nodes, and ISP gateway-level exposures are the three main attack surfaces that are identified and investigated in this study by Alamleh, H. et al. 2025. They presented robustness of WLANs, which is assessed using some practical tests, which range from traffic analysis of ISP-controlled routers to offline password attack modelling. These studies reveal specific vulnerabilities such as credential reuse, firmware-based leakage, and protocol downgrade attacks. The study also shows how formal theories of computational scaling greatly speed up attacks using APT resources. In order to map enemy strategies and contextualise threats, it also integrates threat modelling frameworks such as MITRE ATT&CK and STRIDE. This study provides useful suggestions for improving WLAN resilience through network segmentation, AI-based anomaly detection, open firmware adoption, and enhanced authentication techniques. The results highlight the need for a move toward more resilient, context-aware security architectures since, although present WLAN implementations provide rudimentary defences, they are still quite vulnerable to well-resourced adversaries.

Problem Statement

The shortcoming of the previous research method/protocol on various security attacks is that it makes the router vulnerable because of its critical role; it is only able to detect very limited kinds of attacks. First, to address the aforementioned problems, the TrustR protocol is proposed. Thus, the TrustR framework for protecting computer networks integrates several collaborating security technologies to resist various types of attacks and also introduces a simple but efficient method for detecting deceptive routing messages, and the FIB is updated correctly. However, because of the importance of the problems, further research needs to be carried out to improve the performance of the protocol. To achieve this, the first step in the research process is to reconstruct the simulation of the protocol to verify the results as reported by the authors of the protocol and to establish a benchmark for validation of future research.

The previous research protocol, such as Optimised Link State Routing (OLSR) protocol, Trust and Energy based Ad hoc On Demand Distance Vector (TE-AODV) algorithm, etc. only able to detect very limited kinds of attacks. Furthermore, the Forwarding Information Base (FIB) is rarely protected in current works, while TrustR has been able to defend against all three types of attacks on the router in computer networks (Shuaishuai et.al. 2016).

The Aims and Objectives

The research project aims to design and implement an Integrated Router Security Framework for Protecting Computer Networks with the following objectives:

- i. To improve the Data Packet Delivery Ratio by minimising Black Hole attacks,
- ii. To minimise the Average end-to-end delay by depending on an unauthorised node.

Experimental Tools

Software

Table 1. Summary of Software used

Software	Function
NET	ad hoc routing
Linux (Ubuntu)	Operating System
Virtual Box	Virtualisation software packet
APP	overlay routing protocols
PHY	SNR-based packet capture, broadcast, dynamic transmission rate and power
MAC	IEEE 802.11 (CSMA/CA, virtual carrier sense, and RTS-CTS-DATA-ACK)
MATLAB	Programming Language

Hardware

The computer which is hosted the virtual machines to re-implement this study is an HP TM2 Series (Touch Screen) Laptop with the specifications mentioned in the Hardware table 2 below

Table 2. Summary of Hardware used for Router Security

Hardware	Specification
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i3-7100U CPU @ 2.40GHz 2.40 GHz
RAM	8.00 GB
Storage	HDD 512GB SSD Samsung
Operating System	Microsoft Windows 11, 64-bit operating system, x64-based processor

Experimental Setup

In this study, an Ad-hoc Network topology with 30 nodes will be built, the Ad-hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV) routing protocol will be employed, and the existing wireless network simulator in Matlab will be used for the simulation. There are four data traffic flows that shall be set, and the simulation time of 100s will be set.

Firstly, the Cryptography authentication method proposes the use of random numbers with a timestamp in the nodes to protect the privacy of the nodes. Random numbers are protected with secret values, and the use of hash functions prevents forgery and copying. Also, we use the time frame to provide a solution to prevent replay attacks, and the protection of variable values makes it possible to solve synchronisation problems. The scheme gives an improvement for the authentication between the nodes on the insecure channel in the network.

TrustR Simulation

- ✓ An ad-hoc network topology with 30 nodes will be built
- ✓ The Ad-hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV) routing protocol will be employed
- ✓ Existing wireless network simulator in MATLAB shall be used for the simulation
- ✓ Four data traffic flows shall be set
- ✓ Simulation time of 100s will be set

TrustR Framework Implementation

- ✓ To drive the TrustR framework, first, we employ a **cryptographic authentication method** according to Alomari (2013). This scheme proposes the use of random numbers with a timestamp in the nodes to protect the privacy of the nodes.

Step 1: Explains the authentication process between the source (S) node and the destination (D) node before they start to send and receive the important data. The source node generates a random number r and timestamp T_s and conducts XoR calculation using secret value SV , which the component shares to produce $r \oplus SV$ and $T_s \oplus SV$; the two values are combined to form a hash value $\mathbf{h}(r \parallel T_s)$. The source node sends the $r \oplus SV$ and $T_s \oplus SV$, which are introduced to the destination node.

Step 2: The destination conducts XoR calculation by inputting SV into $r \oplus SV$ and $T_s \oplus SV$ to acquire r and T_s . To authenticate r and T_s , the destination hashes the two values to produce $H(r \parallel T_s)'$ and compares it with $H(r \parallel T_s)$, the hashed value transferred from the source node. When the two values are identical, r and T_s are authenticated. When the destination authenticates from the source values, it starts to produce λ , where λ is the difference between r and T_s and conducts an XoR calculation metaID , where $\text{metaID} = \infty$, to produce $\lambda \oplus \infty$. The hash value $\mathbf{H}(r \parallel \infty)$ is produced and combined with $\lambda \oplus \infty$ to form $\lambda \oplus \infty \parallel \mathbf{H}(r \parallel \infty)$, which is to be sent to the source node for authentication.

Step 3: When the source receives $\lambda \oplus \infty \parallel \mathbf{H}(r \parallel \infty)$ value from the destination, it computes λ again by subtracting r from T_s ($\lambda = r - T_s$). Afterwards, the metaID value is acquired by conducting XoR calculation on the $\lambda \oplus \infty$. To authenticate the acquired metaID (∞), the transferred r is combined to form a hash value $H(r \parallel \infty)'$. If the transferred value $H(r \parallel \infty)$ is identical with the produced $H(r \parallel \infty)'$, the metaID (∞) is authenticated along with the destination with the metaID . Also, the source node computes

metaID = H (ID)' to ensure the ID belong to the destination. To acknowledge the authentication of the destination, the source combines the SV and the variable Ts to form a hash value of H (ID \ \ SV \ \ Ts) and send it to the destination node.

Step 4: When the destination receives the last value from the source node, it starts the verification process by authenticating the hash value H (ID \ \ SV \ \ Ts) that was transferred from the source node. The destination combines SV and Ts to produce a hash value H (ID \ \ SV \ \ Ts). The source and destination mutually authenticate each other. Additionally, after the hash value is authenticated, the destination ID, which is included as a component of the hash value, is also authenticated.

Fig. 2 Random number with secret value and timestamp authentication

Secondly, we employ a trust-based AODV routing mechanism for packet forwarding. The mechanism involves a trust model and energy value calculation; however, the energy value calculation is not utilised in the TrustR framework. More so, Trust Mode involves the following:

- ✓ Direct trust value calculation
- ✓ Indirect trust value calculation: This is also not used in the TrustR Framework.
- ✓ Final Trust Value (FTV)

In this research proposal, four kinds of attacks will be deployed: earliest, unauthorised access to networks, BlackHole that drops all data packets needing to be forwarded, JellyFish that delays all forwarded data packets, and routing spoofing that repeatedly sends deceptive route error messages to make the source node invalidate the current route. In this proposed simulation, the unauthorised node always imposes a JellyFish attack simultaneously, while the attackers (the BlackHole, unauthorised (with JellyFish), and routing spoofing nodes) are gradually added to the networks repeatedly until it reaches the satisfaction level

Fig 3: Router Framework

Algorithm 1

```

1: for all received packets pkt do
2:     if pkt. etherType=NODE and pkt.in Port=HOSTROUTER then
3:         for all switch ports P do
4:             pkt.srcMAC ← P.MACaddr
5:             Send a copy of pkt out on port P
6:         end for
7:     end if
8: end for
    
```

Algorithm 2

```

1: for all received packets pkt do
2:     for all switch ports P do
3:         pkt.srcMAC ← P.MACaddr
4:         send copy of pkt out on port P
5:     end for
6: end for
    
```

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A simple but complete mobile wireless network simulator in MATLAB was used, which provides **Radio propagation**: free space, two-ray, and lognormal shadowing; **Mobility**: random waypoint model; **PHY**: SNR-based packet capture, broadcast, dynamic transmission rate and power; **MAC**: IEEE 802.11 (CSMA/CA, virtual carrier sense, and RTS-CTS-DATA-ACK); **NET**: ad hoc routing and **APP**: overlay routing protocols.

Packets received by the protection system are generated randomly. In case of an unauthorised attack (number of packets > threshold2), the avoidance strategy is implemented. The arrival time and load for each packet are recorded to generate the result’s line chart

Table 3: Experiment Settings: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
Number of Nodes	30
Simulation Time	100s
Mobility	Random waypoint
Network layer	Ad hoc routing
Attacks Beginning Time	101
Threshold1	2000
Threshold2	3000
Normal user Load	0-500
attacker load	2000 – 2700

Fig 4: The number of attacks generated by the sources in the normal case

Fig. 5: The attacks are **decreasing dramatically** after the implementation of the avoidance strategy at time **117 sec**

These results show clearly how effective this strategy is in reducing the traffic load during the unauthorised access attack. Thus, the server can continue to provide its services, especially to the critical users, even in the case of a breach.

The result has shown the ability of TrustR to perform well on the data Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), which illustrates that it can counter BlackHole attacks, and the Average end-to-end delay of TrustR will be much lower, which illustrates that TrustR can defend against the unauthorised nodes which also launch

JellyFish attacks. The less time and the fewer the number, the better the performance. TrustR will perform the best on reducing the route discovery number, which also benefits from the built-in deceptive routing message detector

CONCLUSION

In this research project, we have provided an implementation of an alternative access channel for critical services users, such as governmental or large organisations' servers. A minor delay in service may lead to serious financial, economic, or political consequences. The proposed protection of the router works according to three different scenarios, where it provides service significantly even during the occurrence of an unauthorised access.

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1. Source Code for Black Hole Attack in NS2

```

nsaddr_t malicious1;
nsaddr_t malicious2;
nsaddr_t malicious3;
#code for initialising black hole attackers:
int
AODV::command(intargc, const char*const* argv) {
if(argc == 2) {
Tcl&tcl = Tcl::instance();
if(strncasecmp(argv[1], "id", 2) == 0) {
tcl.resultf("%d", index);
return TCL_OK;
}
if(strcmp(argv[1], "blackhole1") == 0) {
malicious1= index;
printf("malicious %d", malicious1);
return TCL_OK;
}
if(strcmp(argv[1], "blackhole2") == 0) {
malicious2=index;
printf("malicious %d", malicious2);
return TCL_OK;
}
if(strcmp(argv[1], "blackhole3") == 0) {
malicious3= index;
printf("malicious %d", malicious3);
return TCL_OK;
}
AODV::AODV(nsaddr_t id) : Agent(PT_AODV),
btimer(this), htimer(this), ntimer(this),
rtimer(this), lrtimer(this), rqueue() {
index = id;
seqno = 2;
bid = 1;
LIST_INIT(&nbhead);
LIST_INIT(&bihead);
malicious1=999;
malicious2=999;
malicious3=999;a

```

Source Code for Packet Delivery Ratio in NS2

```

% N is the number of nodes in a fully-connected network
N=5;
% W is the contention window size
W=128;
% m is the length of the active period in a cycle (unit: 0.1 ms)
m=285.6;
% Q is the maximum queue size at each node
Q=10;
% lamda is the data arrival rate in the unit of # pkts per ms
lamda=15/10000;
% resolution is the resolution for numerical calculation of p and \pi_0
resolution=0.001;
M=1/resolution;
figure(1)
% Pi_1(i,j) = F[p_1(i,j)] according to the Markov model
% i = 1 -> duty cycle = 10%
% i = 2 -> duty cycle = 30%
% i = 3 -> duty cycle = 50%
% i = 4 -> duty cycle = 70%
% i = 5 -> duty cycle = 90%
p_1=zeros(5,M+1);
Pi_1=zeros(5,M+1);
% p_2(j) = G[Pi_2(j)] according to the media access rules of S-MAC
p_2=zeros(1,M+1);
Pi_2=zeros(1,M+1);
% ps_2(j) is the probability of successfully transmitting a packet at each node
% in a cycle
ps=zeros(1,M+1);
pf=zeros(1,M+1);
p=ps+pf;
% b is the duty cycle
b=-0.1;
for l=1:51
    b=b+0.2;
% T is the cycle length
    T=m*(1-b)/b+1+m; % unit: 0.1 ms
    T=T*0.1 % unit: ms
% px (x=0..50) is the probability that x pkts arrive at a node in a cycle
    p0=exp(-lamda*T)*(lamda*T)^0/1;
    p1=exp(-lamda*T)*(lamda*T)^1/1;
    p2=exp(-lamda*T)*(lamda*T)^2/2;
    p3=exp(-lamda*T)*(lamda*T)^3/6;
    p4=exp(-lamda*T)*(lamda*T)^4/24;
    p5=exp(-lamda*T)*(lamda*T)^5/120;
    p6=exp(-lamda*T)*(lamda*T)^6/720;

```

```

p7=exp(-lamda*T)*(lamda*T)^7/(720*7);
p8=exp(-lamda*T)*(lamda*T)^8/(720*56);
p9=exp(-lamda*T)*(lamda*T)^9/(720*7*8*9);
p10=exp(-lamda*T)*(lamda*T)^10/(720*7*8*9*10);
% ppxy (x=0..10, y=x+1) is the probability that no less than x pakcets arrive at a node in a cycle
pp01 =1;
pp12 =1-p0;
pp23 =1-p0-p1;
pp34 =1-p0-p1-p2;
pp45 =1-p0-p1-p2-p3;
pp56 =1-p0-p1-p2-p3-p4;
pp67 =1-p0-p1-p2-p3-p4-p5;
pp78 =1-p0-p1-p2-p3-p4-p5-p6;
pp89 =1-p0-p1-p2-p3-p4-p5-p6-p7;
pp910 =1-p0-p1-p2-p3-p4-p5-p6-p7-p8;
pp1011=1-p0-p1-p2-p3-p4-p5-p6-p7-p8-p9;
num1=0;
for p=0:resolution:1
    % A is the transition matrix of the Markov model
    A=zeros(17,17);
    A=[1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
        ps (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
        0 ps (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
        0 0 ps (1-p) 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
        0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
        ps 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
        0 ps 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0
        0 0 ps 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0
        0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0
        ps 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0
        0 ps 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0
        0 0 ps 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
        0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0
        p 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0
        0 p 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0
        0 0 p 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0];
    A=A'-eye(17);
    A(17,:)=ones(1,17);
    B=zeros(17,1);
    B(17,1)=1;
    % X0 is the array of stationary probabilities for each state in the Markov model
    X0=A\B; % X0=inv(A)*B
    num1=num1+1;
    ps_1(l,num1)=ps;
    pf_1(l,num1)=pf;
    Pi_1(l,num1)=X0(1);
end

```

```

end;
% h1 is the curve of \pi_0=F(p) according to the Markov model
h1=plot(ps_1(1,:),pf_1(1,:),Pi_1(1,:),'b');
hold on
xlabel('ps');
ylabel('pf');
zlabel('\pi_0');
title(['N=',num2str(N),'          W=',num2str(W),'          Q=',num2str(Q),'
\lambda=',num2str(lamda*10000),'pkt/10s']);
end

% AA(i) is the probability that i-1 out of N-1 nodes in the network are
% contending the media in a cycle
AA=zeros(1,N);
M=zeros(1,N);
Msuc=zeros(1,N);
num2=0;
for pi0=0:resolution:1
    for i=1:N
        co=1;
        for j=1:i-1
            co=co*(N-j);
        end;
        for j=1:i-1
            co=co/j;
        end;
        AA(i)=co*pi0^(N-i)*(1-pi0)^(i-1);
    end;
% ptx is the probability that a node wins the contention when other i-1
% nodes are contending the media
ptx=0;
% ps is the probability that a node successfully transmits a packet
% when other i-1 nodes are contending the media
ps=0;
for i=1:W
    for j=1:N
        M(j)=((W+1-i)/W)^(j-1);
        Msuc(j)=((W-i)/W)^(j-1);
    end;
    for j=1:N
        ptx=ptx+(1/W)*M(j)*AA(j);
        ps=ps+(1/W)*Msuc(j)*AA(j);
    end;
end;
num2=num2+1;
p_2(num2)=ptx;

```

```

Pi_2(num2)=pi0;
ps_2(num2)=ps;
end;
% h2 is the curve of p=G(\pi_0) according to the media access rules of
% S-MAC
h2=plot(p_2,Pi_2,'r');
% Solving \pi_0=F(p) and p=G(\pi_0)
%      ||
%      V
% Finding the intersection of curve (p_1,Pi_1) and curve (p_2,Pi_2)
% pointX(i) is the p of the intersection
% pointY(i) is the \pi_0 of the intersection
% pointK(i) is the corresponding ps
% i = 1..5 corresponding to 5 different duty cycles
pointX=zeros(1,5);
pointY=zeros(1,5);
pointK=zeros(1,5);
% packet delivery ratio of S-MAC under 5 different duty cycles
PDR=zeros(1,5);
% packet delay of S-MAC under 5 different duty cycles, unit: ms
D=zeros(1,5);
% energy over time of S-MAC under 5 different duty cycles, unit: W
energy=zeros(1,5);
b=-0.1;
for l=1:5
    minimum=1;
    b=b+0.2;
    T=m*(1-b)/b+1+m;
    T=T*0.1
    for j=1:num1
        for k=1:num2
            if ((p_1(l,j)-p_2(k))^2+(Pi_1(l,j)-Pi_2(k))^2<minimum)
                minimum=(p_1(l,j)-p_2(k))^2+(Pi_1(l,j)-Pi_2(k))^2;
                pointX(l)=p_2(k);
                pointY(l)=Pi_2(k);
                pointK(l)=ps_2(k);
%----- Packet Delivery Ratio -----
                PDR(l)=(1-pointY(l))*ps_2(k)/(lamda*T);
            end;
        end;
    end;
%----- Delay -----
    p=pointX(l);
    A=zeros(17,17);
    A=[1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
        ps (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0

```

```
0 ps (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 0 ps (1-p) 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
ps 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 ps 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 0 ps 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
ps 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 ps 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0 pf 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 0 ps 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0 0
p 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0 0
0 p 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 (1-p) 0
0 0 p 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0];
```

```
A=A'-eye(17);
A(17,:)=ones(1,17);
B=zeros(17,1);
B(17,1)=1;
```